

Beyond NIS2: Integrating Civil and Defence Cyber to Protect Europe's Critical Functions

Authors

Université Libre de Bruxelles /
Solvay Business School

Palina Shauchuk, Shafagh Kashef, Ievgeniia
Lytvynova and Georges Ataya

Abstract

Europe's critical functions increasingly rely on interconnected digital systems that serve both civilian and defence needs, making cyber incidents more likely to cascade across sectors and borders. Recent ransomware attacks on major transport and health infrastructures show that, despite extensive activity, civil and defence cyber responses remain fragmented, with limited information sharing and situational awareness.

This white paper, developed within the EU-funded COcyber project, argues for moving beyond ad hoc cooperation under NIS2 towards a permanent dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem. It outlines how improved signal sharing, a shared operational picture, and trusted cross-sector relationships can strengthen cyber resilience in practice.

Drawing on international good practices and stakeholder consultations, the paper proposes short-, medium-, and long-term measures to institutionalise civil defence cooperation, reduce disruption to essential services, and better protect Europe's critical functions.

Keywords

Civil-defence cybersecurity, Dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem, Critical infrastructure protection, Cyber crisis management, Cross-sector coordination, Situational awareness, Cyber resilience, Supply-chain cyber risk, Ransomware incidents, Information sharing, Public-private cooperation, European cybersecurity policy, NIS2 implementation, Digital Europe Programme, Innovation hubs

Disclaimer

The COcyber project funded under Grant Agreement No. 101158606 is supported by the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre and funded by the European Union.

Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre. Neither the European Union nor the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre can be held responsible for them.

Copyright notice

© COcyber 2024-2026

Project funded by the European Commission in the Digital Europe Programme

Public – fully open. e.g., website

Sensitive (SEN) – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

EU classified – RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

Table of contents

Executive Summary.....	6
Introduction.....	7
Problem statement.....	8
Practices.....	9
Solution and purpose.....	12
Better flow of signals.....	13
A shared picture of what is happening.....	13
Trusted relationships and clear roles.....	13
What would the ecosystem look like in practice?	14
Short, medium, and long-term mitigating strategies	15
Short-term (0–2 years)	15
Medium-term (2–5 years).....	16
Long-term (5+ years).....	16
Conclusions.....	18

Executive Summary

The COcyber project¹, funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme and embedded in the European Commission's wider portfolio of cybersecurity initiatives, was launched to help Europe strengthen cooperation between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities in responding to fast-moving crises. To ground this work in real operational needs, the project carried out a needs assessment² based on broad consultations with key stakeholders, including civilian operators, national cyber authorities, defence organisations, and critical vendors. The findings of that analysis form the basis of this white paper, which turns the project's evidence and insights into concrete recommendations.

A central lesson is that a single incident can cascade well beyond one organisation. When digital systems fail in a major transport hub, for example, as in the Brussels Airport ransomware incident of 19 September 2025³, an IT disruption can quickly turn into a challenge that affects several sectors and cross- borders.

In this light, the white paper sets out a practical way forward: a permanent dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem, understood as an always-on network of partners, tools, and routines that supports both civilian and defence needs. It focuses on three priorities: improving the flow of signals and information, building a shared operational picture through joint training and exercises, and strengthening trusted relationships with clear roles and agreed guidelines. It also explains how innovation hubs and joint projects can help develop, test, and scale solutions that work across sectors and countries. Together, these elements feed into an operating model designed to make coordinated responses the normal way of working in Europe.

¹ COcyber. (n.d.). Coordination between the cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres. Retrieved December 10, 2025, from <https://cocyber.eu/>

² Université Libre de Bruxelles. (2025, February 4). Deliverable 2.2 Bridging Gaps: A Raw Needs Assessment Report for Enhanced Collaboration Between Civilian and Defence Cybersecurity Spheres (Version v1) [Project deliverable].

³ Brussels Airport. (2025, October 10). 2.3 million passengers in September. Brussels Airport News. <https://www.brusselsairport.be/brusselsairportnews/en/october-2025/2-3-million-passengers-in-september>

Introduction

On September 19, 2025, Brussels Airport and several other major European airports faced severe disruptions that significantly affected their operations. The reason? A ransomware attack that targeted Collins Aerospace's MUSE system, the software used by airlines for check-in and boarding. Suddenly, airlines had to revert to manual check-in systems, causing significant delays and cancellations. At Brussels Airport, around 60 out of 550 flights were affected, with disruptions continuing for days.

Even if this attack was particularly noteworthy, it was just one among many: as digital technologies occupy more space, cyberspace becomes increasingly exposed. These technologies facilitate and accelerate communication and access to information. The flipside is the faster and deeper impact of cyberattacks. The interconnection of different systems also enables more complex and deeper-reaching attacks. Cyberattacks today don't just target computers; they also hit hospitals, power grids, transportation systems, banks, government services, and military networks. Criminal groups, activists, and even hostile states constantly probe for weaknesses.

Traditionally, civilian organisations have focused on data protection and service continuity, whereas defence institutions have safeguarded national security. However, today these domains overlap: the same networks and infrastructure can support both hospitals and military bases. If one side is breached, the other is immediately at risk. The Brussels Airport attack illustrates this interconnection. While the immediate impact was on civilian operations, major transport disruptions also affect defence logistics, troop movements, and emergency response.

Several years ago, the European Commission recognised that cybersecurity needed a more coordinated and comprehensive approach. This insight led to the creation of the COcyber project, in which we were tasked with developing a strategy and roadmap to support greater integration between the civilian and defence sectors, ultimately strengthening the resilience of both.

Problem statement

The Brussels Airport⁴ case shows that Europe still lacks a clear system that links civilian and defence cyber responses⁵. Civilian operators, national cyber authorities, defence organisations, and key vendors often react separately rather than as one team. This pattern is visible in recent incidents such as the Collins Aerospace ransomware attack⁶ affecting Heathrow, Brussels, Berlin and Dublin airports, the Barts Health NHS cyberattack⁷, the Svenska kraftnät data breach⁸, Russian-linked attacks on Polish hospitals and water systems⁹, where airports, hospitals, transmission system operators, national cyber authorities, and vendors issued separate statements and led parallel investigations, while defence structures remained largely absent from operational crisis management. This creates a civil-defence cyber coordination gap, with weak information sharing, limited shared situational awareness, and differences in working culture. Each organisation may perform its role well on its own, but the overall European response remains fragmented¹⁰. This makes it easier for local incidents like the Brussels Airport ransomware attack to spread across sectors and borders, harming both essential services and security.

The COcyber project¹¹, funded by the European Union under the Digital Europe Programme, confirms this picture. Its needs assessment, documented in Deliverable D2.2 and publicly

8

⁴ Brussels Airport, (n.d.) See footnote 3

⁵ Council of the European Union. *Council Recommendation of 6 June 2025 on an EU blueprint for cyber crisis management* (C/2025/3445). OJ C, C/2025/3445, 20.6.2025. EUR-Lex (CELEX: 32025H03445). Council doc. ST/8857/2025/REV/1.

⁶ RTX Corporation. (2025, September 24). *Current report (Form 8-K) on product cybersecurity incident involving MUSE passenger processing software*. U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission, EDGAR database. <https://www.sec.gov/Archives/edgar/data/101829/000010182925000036/rtx-20250919.htm>

⁷ Barts Health NHS Trust. (2025, December 5). *CIOP cyberattack update*. Barts Health NHS Trust. <https://www.bartshealth.nhs.uk/news/ciop-cyberattack-update-18178/>

⁸ Svenska kraftnät. (2025, October 26). *Svenska kraftnät har blivit utsatta för ett dataintrång* [Svenska kraftnät has been subjected to a data breach]. Svenska kraftnät. <https://www.svk.se/press-och-nyheter/nyheter/allmanna-nyheter/2025/svenska-kraftnat-har-blivit-utsatta-for-ett-dataintrang/>

⁹ Polska Agencja Prasowa. (2025, September 16). *Polskie szpitale i wodociągi są atakowane przez hakerów z Rosji. Wiceminister cyfryzacji ujawnia*. PAP.pl. <https://www.pap.pl/aktualnosci/ft-polskie-szpitala-i-miejskie-wodociagi-sa-codziennie-atakowane-przez-hakerow-z-rosji>

¹⁰ European Court of Auditors, *Challenges to effective EU cybersecurity policy*, Briefing Paper, 2019, esp. Executive Summary, paras. V–X. https://www.eca.europa.eu/lists/ecadocuments/brp_cybersecurity/brp_cybersecurity_en.pdf

¹¹ COcyber. (n.d.). See footnote 1

available on Zenodo¹², draws on trusted sources and broad consultations with national cyber authorities, defence bodies, critical-infrastructure operators, and industry representatives. The findings clearly identify coordination and communication weaknesses, limited cross-sector visibility, and insufficient structured information exchange¹³ as key reasons for the civil-defence cooperation gap.

Practices

The September 2025 ransomware incident affecting Collins Aerospace's MUSE check-in and boarding system disrupted operations at Brussels and other major European airports, forcing manual check-in and resulting in delays and cancellations¹⁴. It illustrates how a supplier outage can cascade across interconnected transport systems and borders and how slow or fragmented information sharing between operators, vendors, national cyber authorities, and defence actors undermines a shared operational picture^{15 16}.

To address these coordination gaps, the COcyber project reviewed 296 international practices and identified approaches that consistently improve crisis response: clear playbooks, trusted information-sharing channels, and joint governance and training structures^{17 18}.

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/16760899>

¹³ Needs Assessment Report. See footnote 2

¹⁴ Reuters, 22 September 2025, EU agency confirms ransomware attack behind airport disruptions: <https://www.reuters.com/business/aerospace-defense/eu-agency-says-third-party-ransomware-behind-airport-disruptions-2025-09-22/>

¹⁵ Chang, K., & Huang, H. (2023). Exploring the management of multi-sectoral cybersecurity information-sharing networks. *Government Information Quarterly*, 40(4), 1-14.

¹⁶ Serini, F. (2024). Collective cyber situational awareness in EU. A political project of difficult legal realisation? *Computer Law & Security Review*, 55, 1-12.

¹⁷ From Research to Actionable Practices: <https://cocyber.eu/article-news/deliverable-d41-guidelines-cybersecurity-civil-defence-cooperation>

¹⁸ Pala, A., & Zhuang, J. (2019). Information sharing in cybersecurity: A review. *Decision Analysis*, 16(3), 172-196.

CISA and (Comms-ISAC) ransomware guidance provides a practical ransomware checklist and trusted channels to share indicators quickly, reducing improvisation and speeding coordinated action during fast-moving incidents ¹⁹.

"International Strategy to Better Protect the Financial System Against Cyber Threats" demonstrates how unified protocols and joint crisis exercises help regulators, operators, and system partners act as one, an approach that can be adapted for aviation and transport disruptions ²⁰.

EU CyberNet Operational Guidance on Cyber Capacity Building offers templates for national crisis structures, exercises, and coordination routines, helping define who informs whom, when, and through which secure channels including in civil-defence contexts ^{21 22}.

Translating these strategic priorities into operational practice, EU CyberNet's *Operational Guidance for the EU's International Cooperation on Cyber Capacity Building* (2023 update) provides practical templates for crisis coordination, helping define who informs whom, when, and through which secure channels ²³.

Building on the coordination principles outlined above, the following simplified 24-hour flow illustrates how structured notification and communication routines may operate during the early phase of a cyber incident:

1. Within the first hour (Detection and validation): The operator's security team confirms the incident, opens an incident log, and appoints a single incident lead (clear point of contact).

¹⁹ The Communications Security, Reliability and Interoperability Council V Cybersecurity Information Sharing Working Group 5 FINAL REPORT: <https://www.fcc.gov/sites/default/files/CSRIC5-WG5-FinalReport031517.pdf>

²⁰ International strategy to better protect the financial system against cyber threats: https://carnegie-production-assets.s3.amazonaws.com/static/files/FinCyber_Executive_Summary.pdf

²¹ Cybersecurity in the EU Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP): <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/cybersecurity-eu-common-security-and-defence-policy-csdp-challenges-and-risks-eu>

²² Horizon Europe Work Programme 2025 Civil Security for Society: https://sciencebusiness.net/sites/default/files/inline-files/ec_rtd_he-wp-2025-cluster3-pre.pdf

²³ EU CyberNet (2023). Operational Guidance for the EU's International Cooperation on Cyber Capacity Building. Updated edition. <https://www.eucybernet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/operational-guidance-for-the-eu-international-cooperation-on-ccb-1-1.pdf>

2. Within the first two hours (Internal escalation): The incident lead informs executive management and activates the internal crisis team (IT, operations, legal, communications).
3. Within the first three hours (Notification of national authority): A short, structured notification (what happened, what is affected, what is unknown, immediate containment steps) is sent via the pre-agreed secure channel to the designated national cybersecurity authority responsible for incident coordination.
4. Within the first four hours (Supplier coordination): If a vendor or external system is involved, the operator contacts the supplier using verified secure channels and requests technical guidance and impact confirmation.
5. Within the first six hours (Cross-sector awareness): If the disruption may affect broader infrastructure or civil-defence actors, the national authority shares a sanitised operational update through established coordination mechanisms.
6. Between 6 and 12 hours (Shared operational picture): Stakeholders align on a common situation update and agree on update frequency and responsibilities.
7. Between 12 and 24 hours (Stabilisation and communication): Technical mitigation continues, while communication teams coordinate a clear external message explaining service impact and next steps.

Overall, these practices show that Europe's priority is less about inventing new mechanisms than institutionalising compatible procedures, lawful information-sharing frameworks, and regular joint training so that civil and defence communities can respond as a coordinated network when critical digital services fail.

Solution and purpose

This white paper puts forward a practical way to strengthen Europe's cyber resilience: a dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem²⁴. This means a permanent network of partners, tools, and processes that is designed from the start to serve both civilian and defence needs. Instead of building new structures after every major incident, the ecosystem would be in place at all times, ready to support prevention, response, and recovery across countries and sectors.

Today, Brussels – like most European capitals and major transport hubs – does not yet have such a permanent dual-use system²⁵. Additionally, Europe still lacks systematised, permanent, and scalable examples of effective civil-defence cooperation practices in this field²⁶. Civilian and defence actors do cooperate, for instance, through joint exercises such as NATO's Cyber Coalition²⁷, ECYBRIDGE tabletop simulations²⁸, and EU Cyber Rapid Response Team missions to partners²⁹, but mainly through temporary, case-by-case arrangements activated for specific incidents or training events. The proposed ecosystem is designed to move beyond this ad hoc model.

The ecosystem needs to focus on three concrete areas:

²⁴ European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC). *ECCC Digital Europe Cybersecurity Work Programme 2025-2027*. Version 1 (March 2025). Adopted by the Governing Board of the ECCC in Decision No 2025/04 (also referenced as GB/2025/4); European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre (ECCC). *Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) – Call for proposals: Strengthening the Cybersecurity Ecosystem (DIGITAL-ECCC-2025-DEPLOY-CYBER-08)*. EU Grants: Call document (DEP), Version 1.0 (12 June 2025).

²⁵ European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO). (2025, November 20). *ECSO's Strategic Vision: European cybersecurity 2030*. ECSO (publication/report)

²⁶ COcyber. (2025, November 29). *Deliverable D4.1 Guidelines on Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation* [News post]. COcyber. Accessed 2 December 2025.

²⁷ O'Keeffe, C. (2025, December 3). *Defence Forces take part in world's biggest cyber exercise*. Irish Examiner. <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/arid-41753895.html>

²⁸ ECYBRIDGE. (2025). *Tabletop exercise: Anchoring cyber resilience – Mitigating future threats in a unified digital Europe*. ECYBRIDGE. <https://ecybridge.eu/ecybridge-tabletop-exercise-2/>

²⁹ Ministry of National Defence Republic of Lithuania. (2024, October 23). *EU Cyber Rapid Response Team (CRRT) concludes deployment in support of Moldova's cybersecurity*. <https://kam.lt/en/eu-cyber-rapid-response-team-crrt-concludes-deployment-in-support-of-moldovas-cybersecurity/>

Better flow of signals

Set up shared technical platforms and working routines so that warnings, technical indicators, and impact reports can move quickly between operators, national services, and defence actors. When one side sees a problem, the others know about it in time to act.

A shared picture of what is happening

Organise joint training, workshops, and crisis simulations that regularly bring together experts from different sectors and from both civilian and defence communities. This establishes a common approach to analysing incidents and a shared understanding of the practical meanings of different signals.

Trusted relationships and clear roles

Build long-term partnerships, common guidelines, and regular meetings between public authorities, private operators, and defence organisations. This helps clarify who is responsible for what, what can be shared, and how decisions are taken when time is short.

These elements come together in a network of cybersecurity innovation hubs and joint projects. The hubs offer realistic environments where partners can develop and test tools, procedures, and interfaces together. Joint projects help translate promising ideas into concrete solutions that are ready for use by both civilian operators and defence users.

The purpose of this ecosystem is straightforward: to close the gap between civilian and defence cyber activities in a lasting way. It aims to make fast signal exchange, a common operational picture, and coordinated decision-making the normal way of working in Europe, and to ensure that new cybersecurity solutions can be adopted widely, not just in isolated pockets.

What would the ecosystem look like in practice?

The ecosystem is not a new building or a single new authority. It is a standing, institutionalised way of working that links together key civilian, defence, and private actors through shared tools, agreed procedures, and trusted relationships.

In practical terms, the ecosystem connects: civilian operators (such as airports, hospitals, energy and transport providers), national and regional cyber authorities, defence organisations, key vendors, and EU-level structures. They are connected through agreed-upon contact points, clear escalation paths, and common platforms for sharing technical and operational information in a lawful and secure manner. For a hub like Brussels, this means that the airport, local transport, critical-infrastructure operators, national cyber services, defence bodies, and core suppliers are part of one coordinated, standing network rather than a set of separate circles.

When an incident occurs, the ecosystem changes how the response unfolds. A suspicious pattern detected by a monitoring team is not kept within a single organisation but shared in a standard format with the wider network. Other actors can quickly check whether they see the same indicators, and a joint situation picture is built that shows what is happening, what is affected, and what might be at risk next.

Civilian and defence actors can then align on core priorities and measures, rather than acting in parallel with only partial information. The ecosystem also works in everyday conditions, not only during major crises. Partners use it to exchange smaller warnings and lessons learned, to organise joint training and exercises, and to maintain a common language for classifying incidents and impacts. Over time, this regular contact reduces misunderstandings, builds trust, and facilitates cooperation when time is limited.

For citizens, this ecosystem should mostly remain invisible. They simply experience fewer and shorter disruptions and clearer communication when they do occur. For decision-makers, it provides a stable structure that links policy goals with concrete practices on the ground.

At the same time, building and running such an ecosystem is not without risks and challenges. It requires clear governance to prevent new coordination layers from adding unnecessary bureaucracy, robust safeguards to ensure that information sharing respects legal and

privacy constraints, and sustained investment to keep tools, skills, and procedures up to date. There is also a risk that smaller actors are excluded, or that trust erodes when expectations are raised but not met in practice. Recognising these challenges from the start is essential to ensure that the ecosystem strengthens Europe's cyber resilience without creating new vulnerabilities.

Short, medium, and long-term mitigating strategies

Closing civil–defence coordination gaps requires phased action: quick measures to share signals and align decisions, followed by institutionalised preparedness, and finally a permanent dual-use operating model that can scale across borders ³⁰.

15

Short-term (0–2 years)

Short-term align crisis response in real time. Establish a joint incident room (virtual or physical) that includes operators, vendors, national cyber authorities, law enforcement, and defence cyber teams; use a simple shared incident template to build a common picture; and agree on plain-language public messages for travellers. Early involvement of specialised actors supports faster classification, attribution choices, and protection of sensitive movements that depend on the same infrastructure ^{31 32}.

³⁰ Chance, A. M., Franke¹², V., & Zwarg, T. A. (2025). Strengthening Cyber Resilience by Building Critical Infrastructure Communities: the C-CIC Pilot Study. 201-223.

³¹ Edwards, B., Furnas, A., Forrest, S., & Axelrod, R. (2017). Strategic aspects of cyberattack, attribution, and blame. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(11), 2825–2830.

³² Rid, T., & Buchanan, B. (2015). Attributing cyber attacks. *Journal of strategic studies*, 38(1–2), 4–37.

Because interoperability issues (platforms, formats, and access rules) can block rapid collaboration, short-term protocols should also define minimum technical standards and trusted channels for sharing indicators and impact updates ³³.

Medium-term (2–5 years)

Medium-term build shared preparedness and reduce friction. Run regular joint civil–defence exercises based on “MUSE-style” supplier outages; harmonise basic terminology and thresholds for escalation; strengthen supplier and supply-chain obligations (reporting, participation in exercises, tested fallbacks); and expand joint training so mixed teams interpret signals and consequences in the same way ³⁴.

To sustain cooperation, governance must address trust, incentives, and clear policy frameworks; otherwise, information-sharing networks weaken over time, even when technical tools exist ³⁵.

Long-term (5+ years)

In the long term, establish a permanent dual-use cyber ecosystem. Create standing cooperation platforms linking critical operators, national cyber authorities, defence organisations, and key vendors; develop innovation hubs and joint projects to test and scale shared tools and dashboards; and define an EU-level coordination function for major multi-country incidents to build a coherent shared situational picture ³⁶.

³³ Rantos, K., Spyros, A., Papanikolaou, A., Kritsas, A., Ilioudis, C., & Katos, V. (2020). Interoperability challenges in the cybersecurity information sharing ecosystem. *Computers*, 9(1), 1–17.

³⁴ Guidance for organisations to build supply chain resilience against ransomware: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/supply-chain-resilience-against-ransomware/guidance-for-organisations-to-build-supply-chain-resilience-against-ransomware>

How to Prevent Supply Chain Ransomware Attacks: <https://www.veeam.com/blog/ransomware-attacks-supply-chain-2025.html>

The rise of ransomware attacks and the business impacts for your supply chain: <https://www.pwc.com.au/cyber-security-digital-trust/ransomware-in-the-supply-chain.html>

³⁵ Sedenberg, E. M., & Dempsey, J. X. (2018). Cybersecurity information sharing governance structures: An ecosystem of diversity, trust, and tradeoffs. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.12266*, 1–27.

³⁶ Trimintzios, P., Network, E. U. A. f., & Security, I. (2017). *Cybersecurity in the EU Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP): Challenges and Risks for the EU: Study*. Scientific Foresight Unit (STOA), Directorate for Impact Assessment

Together, these measures translate lessons from the Brussels Airport incident into a predictable operating model in which signals move quickly, situational awareness is shared, and decisions are coordinated, reducing disruption for citizens while protecting Europe's critical functions and security.

Atapour-Abarghouei, A., McGough, A. S., & Wall, D. S. (2020). Resolving the cybersecurity data sharing paradox to scale up cybersecurity via a co-production approach towards data sharing. 2020 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)

Conclusions

This white paper shows that Europe's cyber resilience is weakened not by a lack of activity, but by the fact that civilian and defence efforts still operate in parallel. The recent incidents confirm the pattern: each organisation acts within its mandate, yet cross-sector crises are still managed with fragmented information and only partial coordination.

We propose the dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem as a structural response to this problem. It is not a new authority or a temporary task force, but a permanent way of working that connects existing actors and capabilities. Its added value lies in making routine what is now exceptional: rapid signal exchange across sectors, a shared operational picture, and coordinated decisions in both everyday work and crisis situations.

Through co-design work with practitioners, the COcyber project has taken a first step by translating these requirements into a concrete ecosystem concept. Implementing such an ecosystem is feasible using existing tools and institutions. The main effort is organisational and political: clarifying roles, agreeing on a limited set of common platforms and hubs, and giving them sustained support. At the same time, governance, legal constraints, and inclusiveness cannot be afterthoughts. Without clear rules, strong safeguards, and attention to smaller and regional actors, the ecosystem would struggle to build and maintain trust. If these conditions are met, incidents like the Brussels Airport ransomware case should become less frequent, less disruptive, and less likely to spread across sectors and borders.

Europe already has important building blocks for such structured cooperation. Information Sharing and Analysis Centres (ISACs), supported at the EU level by ENISA³⁷, provide trusted environments for sector-specific information exchange among critical operators. ISACs facilitate the sharing of threat intelligence, indicators of compromise, vulnerabilities, and mitigation practices within sectors such as energy, transport, finance, and health. However, these mechanisms remain primarily sector-focused and largely civilian in orientation. A future dual-use cybersecurity ecosystem should therefore build upon existing ISAC structures while strengthening structured interfaces with defence cyber actors. Connecting, rather than duplicating, these established information-sharing communities would enhance

³⁷ See ENISA, Information Sharing and Analysis Centres (ISACs), available at: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/cybersecurity-of-critical-sectors/information-sharing-and-analysis-centers-isacs>

cross-sector situational awareness while preserving the trust-based governance models that make ISACs effective.

Next, the European Union should act first by defining a simple common baseline (how signals are shared, who to contact, and minimum rules for cooperation) and funding a few pilot hubs. Member States should then implement it by appointing national dual-use contact points to link civilian cyber authorities with defence cyber bodies and by running pilots with key operators and vendors. If the pilots prove successful, the model should be scaled EU-wide, while daily operations remain managed at the national and local levels.